

Study of water quality of three major rivers of Bhutan

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Abstract : The Punatshang Chu, Thimphu Chu and Pa Chu are rivers located in three different districts of Punakha, Thimphu, and Paro respectively and drain the region of Western Bhutan. These rivers ultimately drain their water in Brahmaputra, which is one of the major rivers that flow through the North East region of India towards Bay of Bengal. These rivers are of great economic importance since they have been extensively utilized for the generation of hydropower, agriculture and domestic purposes. This study is based upon short-term data collected consisting of parameters such as pH, conductivity, TDS, turbidity, alkalinity, hardness, DO, BOD, COD, chloride, sulphate, phosphate, sodium, potassium, lithium, calcium, lead, chromium from 15 different sampling spots that were selected along the course of these three rivers. Based on the analysis report the quality of the river water in these rivers is affected by the anthropogenic activities such as unsanitary condition along the banks, improper disposal of solid wastes and the untreated domestic wastewaters discharged directly into them. Addressing this issue, the quality of water can be improved and further deterioration can be curbed by taking appropriate measures involving the government authority and active community participation.

Keywords : BOD, COD, DO, IPM, TDS.

Introduction

Water being over 70% of the Earth's surface, is undoubtedly the most precious natural resource in our planet, but we disregard it by polluting our rivers, lakes, and oceans. Subsequently, we are harming our planet to the point where organisms are dying at a very alarming rate. In order to combat water pollution, we must make solution by understanding the problems.

Fresh water is available in abundance in Bhutan and the quality of river water is regarded to be pretty good. Due to rapidly growing urban population, pollution free water is a critical challenge in the future. The pressure on the water resources is mounting due to competing demands from agriculture, hydropower and other industries.

Quality of water is decreasing due to water pollution, but also threatens human health and the balance of aquatic ecosystem. Economic development and social prosperity consumption and use of this contaminated water for both

domestic and agriculture purpose is a key cause of several diseases.

The anthropogenic activities which influence the river water quality in these rivers can be grouped as domestic wastewater, untreated sewage and agriculture run-off. This study can be useful for establishment like National Environment Commission (NEC) which can ultimately play a major role in creating awareness to the people about the impacts of water pollution.

In brief, the global water crisis is a battle towards our civilization. A well designed and properly financed national plans can drive to extend access to water and sanitation to all, backed by a global plan of action to galvanize political will, mobilize resources¹⁻³ and ultimately creating awareness to the masses so that we can afford an access to unpolluted fresh water in the years to come.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Materials : All chemicals were of analytical grade

and were purchased from SD Fine Chemicals (Bombay, India). All samples were prepared using double distilled water following AWWA protocol⁴.

Methods : pH was determined by using pH meter (Systronics Digital pH meter MK VI, Sr. No. 5789). Conductivity and TDS was analysed by using Conductivity Meter (308, Sr. No. 458). Turbidity was determined by using nephelometric turbidimeter (Nephlo-Turbidity meter 132). Alkalinity was determined by titration method using 0.02 N H₂SO₄. Hardness was determined by EDTA titrimetric method using 0.01 M EDTA and Eriochrome Black T as indicator. Dissolved Oxygen was determined by Winkler's method using dilution water. BOD was determined by analyzing oxygen content by Winkler's method using dilution water. Alkali metals like lithium, sodium, potassium and calcium were analysed by using flame photometer (Systronics flamephotometer-128). Heavy metals like lead and chromium were determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AA 240). Microbial study was done by Grams staining method.

Sample collection : In each river five sampling spots were selected, keeping a minimum of 5 km distance in-between two spots. Along the main course of Punatshang Chu five spots were selected namely Phuensum Pelri Palace, below Punakha Higher Secondary School (PHSS), Khurthang Bridge, below Vocational Training Institute, Samthang and Wangdue Bridge. In case of Thimphu Chu also five spots were selected namely Tango Cheri, Dechenchholin Bridge, Changzamtok, Namseling and Khasadrapchu Bridge. In Pa Chu the spots selected were Lango Bridge, Rinpung Dzong Bridge, below Imtrat Canteen, Bondey, Isuna and Zapchukha. These areas are exposed to different human interference with variable degree of pollution to the river water. In the six months period the samples were collected three times – first one in second week of December, second one in first week of February and third one in third week of April.

Three types of samples were collected such as preserved, non-preserved and microbial activity from each particular spot. The preserved and non-preserved samples were collected in the mineral water bottles and for the microbial activity a special type of autoclaved microbial bottles covered by aluminium foil were used⁴⁻⁷. The preserved sample was filtered using the Whatmann filter paper

and 1 ml of concentrated nitric acid was added per litre of the water sample to preserve it. A special care was given to the microbial activity while collecting the water samples. The bottles were opened at least 1 foot under the water surface; the samples were collected and again the bottles were closed under the surface of water.

Analytical procedure : The collected samples were analyzed for pH, conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, turbidity, alkalinity, hardness, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), chloride, sulphate, phosphate, metallic ions such as lithium, sodium, potassium, and calcium, heavy metals such as lead, chromium, and microbial activity for three different periods in triplicate analyses.

A part of the analysis during the second round of sample collection was carried out at Babesa Sewage Treatment Plant and Jungshina Water Treatment Plant in Thimphu, Bhutan. The HACH Company's digital equipments and ready-made reagents were used for analysis of the water parameters. This was done mainly to compare the result of analysis done immediately after collection with that of analysis done in our department's laboratory.

Results and discussion

All the analysis of the water parameters were carried out using the analytical reagents from laboratory and some from Sd fine Chemicals Limited following the standard methods and equipment available. The following data collected for different parameters were recorded thrice between December to April keeping a gap of almost one and half months between the each analysis from three rivers of Bhutan.

pH : The pH values (7.2–9.9) obtained shows that the water is slightly alkaline due to the presence of domestic effluents apart from carbonates, bicarbonates and hydroxides in water. The alkalinity may also be due to the weathering of rocks along the course of the river.

Conductivity : The value obtained shows that the water has high concentration of total dissolved solids, total concentration of ions and suspended particles. This could be mainly due to the domestic effluents that are released into the river along its course. Another reason could be due to the fast current of the river water that erodes the

soil particles and other minerals along its course as it flows downhill.

Turbidity : There is slight variation in the average turbidity values (2.7–4.8 NTU) among these three rivers with Punatshang Chu being the most turbid (Ave. 4.7 NTU) which depends on the type of soil over which water runs and the velocity of run-off.

Hardness : The values obtained (33.1–66.2 mg/L) shows that water is moderately hard. It could be mainly due to the domestic sewage from kitchen and bathroom and improper disposal of wastes, apart from carbonates, bicarbonates and hydroxides present in water.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) : The values obtained (6.7–9.3 mg/L) from analysis show that the water is highly oxygenated and the level of pollution is low. This could be mainly due to dilution effect as all these rivers are joined by many tributaries and small streams whose water are of pristine quality.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) : The value obtained (0.04–0.19 mg/L) is very low i.e. below 1 mg/L which shows that the river water is not polluted much. Among them Thimphu Chu has the highest BOD value (Ave. 0.19 mg/L), this could be mainly due to greater number of human settlements along the course of the river and anthropogenic activities, rainfall which is slowly changing the natural environment of the river.

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) : Punatshang Chu and Thimphu Chu have the highest COD value (7.2–7.6 mg/L). The high value obtained in these two rivers could be due to the accumulated domestic effluents that are released directly into the river from different towns which has developed in the valley along the course of the river due lack of proper sewage treatment plants and improper disposal of untreated wastes into the stream from the automobiles workshop in Messsina deteriorates the quality of Punatshang Chu which can worsen the situation in the

future if proper attention is not given to it.

Phosphate : Among these rivers Thimphu Chu has the highest phosphate value (Ave. 14.2 mg/L). The high phosphate value obtained in all the three rivers is mainly due to domestic sewage, agricultural run-off and use of synthetic detergents containing phosphate and overflow of the septic tanks into the river that has cropped up in the valley along the course of the river.

Chloride : There is not much difference in the average chloride value among these three rivers. Among them Punatshang Chu has the highest chloride value (0.4 mg/L) which could be due to domestic effluents containing NaCl that come from the kitchen and domestic sewage into the river.

Calcium : There is a variation in the average calcium content among these three rivers (Ave. 12.5–24.2 mg/L). Among them Thimphu Chu has the highest calcium value (Ave. 24.2 mg/L). This could be due to the nature of the soil and the surface over which river is flowing.

Potassium, sodium and lithium : There is not much difference in the average values of potassium (Ave. ~0.5 mg/L), sodium (< 0.1 mg/L) and lithium (< 0.1 mg/L) among these three rivers. Among them Punatshang Chu has the highest potassium value.

Heavy metals : The water samples from all these three rivers were analyzed for heavy metals like lead and chromium. The concentrations of them were less than 0.1 mg/L. The only reason could be that there is no source of heavy metal pollution except from the exhaust fumes of automobiles for lead.

Microbial activity : A study on the types of bacteria present in the river water was done by Grams staining method. It was observed that all the sampling spots showed the presence of both Gram-positive bacteria and Gram-negative bacteria. It basically consisted of *Bacillus* and *Coccus* (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria present in river water. (a) *Anthrax*, (b) *S. bacillus*, (c) *Streptococcus*, (d) *E. coli* and (e) *P. aeruginosa*.

Table 1. Results on different parameters analysed from three rivers in Bhutan

R-1 : Punatshang Chu; R-2 : Thimphu Chu; R-3 : Pa Chu; 1 : pH; 2 : conductivity (mhos/cm); 3 : turbidity (NTU); 4 : hardness (mg/L); 5 : DO (mg/L); 6 : BOD (mg/L); 7 : COD (mg/L); 8 : phosphate (mg/L); 9 : chloride (mg/L); 10 : calcium (mg/L); 11 : potassium (mg/L); others (Na, Li, Pb and Cr) < 0.1 mg/L; ## : Recommended level

Rivers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R-1	8.2	102.8	4.7	33.1	9.3	0.04	7.6	9.3	0.41	12.5	0.52
R-2	8.3	167.7	3.8	66.2	9.4	0.19	7.2	14.2	0.31	24.2	0.45
R-3	8.1	151.5	2.7	58.9	6.7	0.18	3.94	12.8	0.29	17.9	0.50
## ⁸	6-9	< 500	50	> 100	> 5	50	250	< 5	0.50	< 1000	0.05

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the study that Bhutan's water resources at the macro level is in a very good condition which comparable to other study⁸⁻¹². There are localized water pollution problems occurring in some of the places as we compare the present data with the previous ones. Some of the parameters like pH, COD, phosphate and some of the metal ions like calcium have increased over the years. This is mainly due to anthropogenic activities and the settlements that have developed in the valley along the banks of these rivers but the problem is not so enhanced. We cannot become complacent about it. There is still a lot to improve and the general public has to be educated and made aware of the consequences of the pollution.

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